

Classroom Data Collection for Teachers' Data-Informed Practice

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Research indicates that data-informed practice helps teachers change their teaching and promotes teacher professional development (TPD). Although educational data is often collected from digital spaces, in-action evidence from physical spaces is seldom gathered, providing an incomplete view of the classroom reality. Also, most learning analytics tools focus on learners and do not explicitly collect or analyse teaching data. To support teacher-led inquiries in TPD, our Design-Based Research explores the feasibility and effects of teachers actively collecting, with the help of technology, data about their classroom practice and the possible impact of such data on their own teaching. Based on an online survey (N=94) and prior research literature, the paper gives an overview of teacher data needs, and provides feedback from teachers (N=11) who used two data collection tools (EduLog and Prolearning) in their classrooms. Summarising lessons learned from these studies (demonstrating the feasibility of such data collection), we suggest design principles for classroom data collection tools, as apart from usability and ease of use we also detected interest in customization, triggering teacher interest and inclusion of teaching data.

Keywords: classroom data collection, classroom observation tools, teaching analytics, teacher professional development and action research, technology design principles

1 Introduction

Despite the fact that data-informed practice has been widely recognized (Feng et al., 2016) and is effectively used in different fields from business to medicine, the use of educational data by teachers to improve teaching in the classroom has not become common or widespread (Kaufman et al., 2014). In their everyday practice, teachers observe students' behaviour, consider assessment data, and estimate the effectiveness of their own teaching strategies (Gummer & Mandinach, 2015). However, teachers often adapt their teaching based on their intuition and experience (Schildkamp & Kuiper, 2010),

considering what they notice in their classroom and limited observations (Ingram et al., 2004) rather than purposely collected data.

In this paper, we employ the definition of ‘data in the context of education’ by Lai & Schildkamp (2013) as ‘information that is systematically collected and organized to represent some aspect of schools’ (p.10) and focus on individual teacher and classroom-level data and improvements (Mandinach et al., 2006). However, in addition to data, evidence can also be derived from other sources (e.g. teacher observations of student engagement, etc), which inform practice.

Why is data-informed practice still rare among teachers when it is being promoted through different reforms (Datnow & Hubbard, 2016)? One reason might be the nature of the available data. Namely, there is a growing body of research studies about automatic data collection in education (such as Educational Data Mining or Learning Analytics, which often use data from Learning Management Systems or LMSs). However, such research focuses mainly on students’ online learning activities (Datnow & Hubbard, 2016; Kaufman, et al., 2014; Schildkamp et al., 2016; Supovitz, 2013), which aim at informing practitioners about students’ learning habits and potential problems. Few research studies have been devoted to the **alignment of the available data with teacher needs and school affordances** (such as teaching in the physical classroom, time constraints, etc.). One overview of actual inquiry questions that teachers take an interest in can be found in a literature review by Dyckhoff et al. (2013), who provide a classification of question categories (which we will compare our findings with) asked by teachers in Technology Enhanced Learning.

Also, little data are collected and available about **teacher activities**. One line of research is focused on the analysis of the learning designs created by teachers (Rienties & Toetenel, 2016; Hernández-Leo, et al., 2019; Sergis, et al., 2019). Another is centred around teacher reflection, which is based on either teacher diaries (post-action reflections), resource-bound video-recordings (Supovitz, 2013), outsider observations (Datnow & Hubbard, 2016; Hubers et al., 2016), or eye-tracking

(Mangaroska & Giannakos, 2018; Prieto, et al., 2015). However, these data-collection methods have not become part of teachers' daily routine, and most of the decisions about classroom practice are still made by teachers using their common sense and pedagogical knowledge.

Dyckhoff et al. (2013) highlight that Learning Analytics (LA) tools should address this issue by explicitly **collecting, analysing and presenting teaching data** because neglecting the significant factor of teacher actions during a teaching/learning process hinders holistic inquiry (Sergis & Sampson, 2017) and important questions of teachers remain unanswered by LA tools. Therefore, our study investigates two possibilities for teachers' classroom data collection about their own activities (one helps to collect activity logs from the physical classroom and the other students' feedback on the teaching process).

To gain a more realistic picture of the teaching process, **data from physical spaces** should be collected in addition to automatic online data (from LMSs and quizzes). As teachers in a physical classroom are usually involved in several activities and have multiple aspects to deal with, the means for deliberate in-action data collection are rather limited. Nowadays, several technological possibilities, such as wearable cameras and eye-tracking devices (Estepa & Amador, 2016; Prieto et al., 2015) for classroom observation have been proposed, which could help to solve some of the aforementioned issues (e.g., teacher autonomy in data collection, i.e., no need for outside observers). However, as these options have not yet become widely used (either because of lack of dissemination, teacher awareness, complexity for everyday use, or other issues), they should be developed further or new data collection possibilities should be provided, considering teachers' data needs and classroom constraints (Kaufman et al., 2014). One of the aims of this study is to test the feasibility of teacher-led classroom data collection with the help of (mobile) technology.

There is also relatively little research into the ways how teachers analyse or make sense of data or how they **incorporate data into their teaching practice** (Supovitz, 2013). Teachers regularly analyse, interpret, and make decisions based on assessment data and achievement scores (Datnow &

Hubbard, 2016; Hubers, et al., 2016; Kaufman et al., 2014; Pierce et al., 2013; Reeves & Honig, 2015; Schildkamp, et al., 2016; Supovitz, 2013). However, they rarely collect additional data about their teaching (Mandinach, 2012) and, even less, relate such evidence to student success and development (Ingram, et al., 2004).

Furthermore, studies often focus on the skills and knowledge that teachers need in order to use data in their work, for example, to regroup students or to offer additional support (Goertz et al., 2009), rather than on **possibilities for changing teaching practice**. Although in recent times researchers cooperate with teachers more often in order to better address their needs (Martinez-Maldonado, et al., 2020; Holstein et al., 2017), scarcity of research into teachers' actual data needs (e.g. from physical spaces and about teaching) might be one of the reasons why data-informed practice in the classroom has not become common yet. Educators find it important to use data in a way that has pragmatic uses in their day-to-day practice (Jimerson & Wayman, 2015). The present study explores how teacher-collected data about their own activities in the classroom could inform their practice.

The previously described problems (as summarized in Table 1) have led us to our main research question for this paper: **How can technology support teachers in data collection for data-informed practice?** To answer it, we worked together with a total of 109 Estonian practitioners teaching at different educational levels and focused on three problem areas that triggered our research: 1) Teachers' data-needs; 2) Technology for classroom data collection; 3) Possible impact of the collected data on teachers' practice. These problem areas derive from the need for evidence that would demonstrate whether Estonian teachers have adopted the concepts outlined in the Estonian Lifelong Learning Strategy 2020. Namely, when changing towards a student-centred approach to learning, teachers also need evidence that they are moving in the right direction.

[Here Table 1]

The next sections provide an overview of our Design Based Research (DBR) methodology and a summary of the results of our iterative studies, followed by a list of the lessons learned (with qualitative and quantitative evidence supporting them). We will also point out some limitations and thoughts for further research.

2 Methodology

The research aim of this work is twofold: a) to test how data collection with technological tools from physical classrooms would enable teachers to make informed decisions about their teaching, and b) to get practitioner opinions on the feasibility of such data collection and its usefulness, in order to enhance tool design. Therefore, we follow the Design Based Research (DBR) methodology (Wang & Hannafin, 2005), which allows addressing complex problems in real educational contexts in collaboration with practitioners (with the aim of working out design principles). In order to answer our main research question (how can technology support teachers in data collection for data-informed practice), we set out to explore three sub-questions: 1) How could teachers use data to learn about their own teaching? 2) Which technology would cater for teachers' data-collection needs and affordances in a physical classroom? 3) How would such data help teachers make decisions about their practice?

As depicted in Figure 1, our DBR process spans 4 studies distributed across 3 iterations. The first iteration is a teacher survey (N=94) into teachers' present data use and preferences for data-collection technology. From the comparison of our survey results with research literature we indicate teachers' data needs, which lead to the choice of tools (Prolearning and EduLog, developed for these purposes by our researchers) for our second iteration, where teachers (N=15) collect data in their own classrooms. As the second iteration is mostly concerned with the ease of use and usability of the tools in real classrooms, the third iteration aims at making such data-collection more sustainable by asking the teacher to pose his/her own concrete inquiry questions that they need the data for. So, the third

iteration is a longer (8 months) action research case with multiple tool usage, where a teacher (N=1) does not just try out data-collection tools but collects data to answer her own inquiry questions.

Our main data collection means are participatory design methods (including questionnaires and interviews) and log data generated by the authentic use of the tools in schools. For data analysis we employ mixed methods, such as descriptive statistics and qualitative (thematic) analysis. The three authors first analysed the data on their own, generating initial categories from the data. Then the outcome was compared, discussed and data revisited to synthesize ‘lessons learned’ and recommendations for the design of teacher-led data collection tools usable in physical classrooms. The process was repeated for each data set until consensus was reached between the researchers.

[Here Figure 1]

2.1 Iteration 1. Teacher survey and literature (Study 1)

To investigate teachers’ data-needs from physical classrooms, an online teacher survey was carried out in spring 2018 and the results were compared with findings from related research literature. The survey explored teachers’ present data collection habits and inquired about their data needs and readiness to use technological tools for data collection (what data they would collect and what technology they would be ready to use to collect data in their classroom).

As the aim of the survey was to get an initial understanding of teachers’ practice with data and their expectations, a convenience sample (N=94) was used (teachers from primary, secondary and tertiary levels, both formal and informal education, were approached to detect possible differences in their needs, but mainly school teachers responded). The survey data were analysed using descriptive statistics (5-point Likert scale) and thematic analysis (for open-ended questions about TPD interests). The aspects that teachers would like to improve in (e.g. time-management, organizing group-work, motivating students, etc.) were organized into data categories by two researchers independently and

then discussed together to identify teachers' data needs. Very specific needs (learning new methods or digital skills and robotics, etc.) were left out as they are not in the scope of the present study. The resulting 'data needs' categories were then compared with the 'question categories' identified by Dyckhoff et al. (2013) to inform the selection of the data collection tools for our next iterations.

2.2 Iteration 2. Data collection in the classroom (Studies 2-3)

The second iteration included two studies where teachers used a technological tool to collect data from their own classrooms. In study 2, six (N=6) officially-recognized expert teachers (7-41 years of teaching experience, all female, teaching languages or mathematics) from primary to secondary education, volunteered to use a student feedback tool (Prolearning: <http://prolearning.realto.ch/>) in their classroom for two weeks and participate in the survey. In study 3, nine teachers (N=9, 1 from kindergarten, 6 from lower and/or upper secondary education and 2 university lecturers), out of which 5 were from the previous sample, volunteered to use a classroom observation tool (EduLog: <http://web.htk.tlu.ee/edulog>) to collect classroom activity data (the length and sequence of activities).

The Prolearning tool (Prieto et al., 2020) enables teachers to ask for quick student feedback (1-2 minutes) and compare the means of students' responses with the teacher's predictions about them, i.e. compare the students' perceptions about their learning with the teacher's (Figure 3). As the tool is customizable, the teacher can prepare a short questionnaire (yes/no questions and percentage questions) prior to the class and pose the questions that they are genuinely interested in (e.g. student motivation, preparedness for and progress in the lesson, or a predicted test score). The data visualization shows means of the students' responses (in columns) and the teacher's predictions (a line graph).

[Here Figure 3]

Another tool, EduLog (Authors, 2018), makes it possible for teachers to log their own teaching process and see the length and pattern of classroom activities. This way the teacher can compare their lesson plan with the actual lesson situation, explore whether the teacher or students were more active in

the class, assess the balance between the activities (e.g., individual vs group work) or variety in activity types (Figure 4). This tool is also customizable (the teacher can alter the button names for the activities and lesson goals) and does not require much preparation from the teacher before the lesson (only to start a session and provide it a name). During teaching, the teacher just records the beginning of each new activity (by pressing a button on their phone or computer, depending on which device they use). The system records the length of different activities and shows the lesson pattern as a bar chart: the upper bars in the graph show teacher-led activities and the lower rows students' activities (in seconds).

[Here Figure 4] Considering the constraints of physical classrooms (teacher's multiple tasks, time-management, possible impact of any outside observers) the tools were used by expert teachers to avoid excessive stress during teaching, since experts are more flexible in their teaching practice (Berliner, 2001). All participants signed an informed consent at the beginning of our collaboration and also provided their tool data for analysis, (which complies with the ethical regulations of the university).

Both studies in this iteration were structured similarly: after a short instruction on the tool use, teachers collected data for two weeks in their own classrooms. Online questionnaires were used to collect teachers' opinions about the tools, and to find out how such data collection and analysis would help teachers improve their classroom practice. A 5-point Likert scale, based on the Technology Acceptance Model (Venkatesh & Davis, 2000), was used to explore the Perceived Usefulness and Perceived Ease of Use of the proposed technology as well as the Intent to Use it in the future. We also asked participants' suggestions for the improvement of the tool and asked about the suitability of the tool/analytics for different user groups. Such data collection is consistent with other relevant studies in the field (Ali et al., 2012), which involved teachers as participants evaluating tools for educators.

To triangulate the results and find out about any possible long-term impact of classroom data

collection with the tools, as well as to detect any further usage, log data was analysed and post-intervention interviews were conducted 8-10 months afterwards, with the teachers who had expressed their willingness to continue using the tools for their informed classroom practice. The interview questions followed the same line as the Likert scale questionnaire and posed for more elaborate explanations of the answers. The tool-use questionnaires were analysed using descriptive statistics and interview data were coded by three authors separately and then discussed together to detect the lessons learned about all the three topics that triggered the study (Table 2).

2.3 Iteration 3. Multiple tool use for action research

The third iteration was conditioned by the fact that although teachers found the tools easy to use and the data useful, further adoption (based on log data) was not detected. Our assumption was that teachers do not see the benefits of data collection and analysis unless there is a more specific goal that data collection would help to solve. Thus, our third iteration was a case study where a teacher collected data with the two previously-tested tools in order to inform her decisions about her teaching, as part of an action research. The teacher used the tools with 14-year-old students in her project-type foreign language classes about twice a month, for a whole school year. Her aim was twofold: 1) to limit the time spent on individual tasks in the classroom and promote group-work and communication between students; 2) to direct students towards becoming self-driven learners (setting individual goals and analysing their own development). Our aim was to see if she was able to collect classroom data to make decisions for changing her practice accordingly and if a clear research aim would promote long-term data collection. Her feedback was collected through an interview and compared with the log data from the tools.

The following sections give an overview of the results and evolution of this DBR process over three iterations. The evidence collected through these studies, and the lessons we have synthesized from it (along the three topics outlined above), are summarized in Section 4.

3 Results

Through the three DBR iterations described in the previous sections, we collected evidence to answer our main research question: ‘How can technology support teachers in data collection for data-informed practice?’ For each research topic (see Figure 1), Table 2 provides the main findings and lessons learned, along with selected qualitative and quantitative evidence. Each piece of evidence is coded according to the study (S1-S4) and the data-gathering technique (interview, questionnaire, or log data from the tools used).

[Here Table 2]

3.1 Iteration 1: Focus on teachers’ data needs (Study 1)

Our online survey of N=94 teachers aimed at finding out about teachers’ data-needs when teaching in a physical classroom, and revealed that 76% of the participant teachers (n=71) would like to be better at developing self-driven learners (they would explore student motivation, their involvement in class, providing timely feedback to students, accounting for the needs of different students depending on their level, learning style, etc.); and 73% of the teachers (n=70) would monitor the diversity of their classroom activities. Other main aspects indicated by the teachers included: flexibility, better planning, issues related to group work, triggering interest in students, paying attention to every student, etc., Based on these findings, we identified three categories that teachers in a physical classroom would collect data about: time management and flexibility; diversity of classroom activities; and student motivation and feedback.

Out of different data collection technologies teachers would use mobile applications (for student feedback, n=71 and classroom activity data, n=59), video-recordings (n=38) and some sensor data (n=48 brain-sensors, n=56 room sensors). Also, the teachers pointed out that the main aspects hindering their professional development are time constraints and workload, which is very important to consider

when designing tools for classroom data collection.

When we compared our findings with teacher question categories identified by Dyckhoff et al. (2013), who in their literature review analyse research about online learning, we could match four out of their six teacher inquiry categories (quantitative - length of student involvement, qualitative - students' rating of learning offerings, data consolidation – which activities facilitate learning, effects on performance) with our three categories (Figure 4) and assessment data (not in our focus). To collect the necessary data for these categories, it is possible to use classroom **activity logs** (for time management, flexibility and diversity of classroom activities), **while student feedback** (about the learning activities and students' own development) could be used to learn about student motivation and feedback on their studies. These, in turn, could be compared with student results (effects on performance in Dyckhoff et al., 2013). Therefore, in the following iterations, we focus our efforts on collecting classroom activity logs and student feedback, and use two tools that our researchers have developed for these purposes.

3.2 Iteration 2: Testing the feasibility of technological data collection tools meant for the physical classroom (Studies 2-3)

To understand the feasibility and possible impact of collecting classroom activity logs and student feedback, we tested two technological tools, Prolearning and EduLog, which the teacher can use for data-collection in a physical classroom. If student test scores were, for example, compared with the data from these two tools, the teacher would get a more holistic view of the teaching process and could make more data-informed decisions about their classroom practice. Results from these studies are grouped according to our research topics and are presented in Table 2.

From the feedback from ten different teachers who used both tools for in-action data collection we found out that, despite some limitations, such easy but meaningful data collection is possible and also suitable for informing teachers' practice (see the evidence in Table 2). Almost all teachers (n=9) agreed that the tools helped them reflect on their teaching and made them consider introducing some

changes into their teaching. What they all agreed about is the fact that the data collection process itself made them more aware of their own teaching and really think about their teaching methods and lesson planning. Teachers found the tools feasible, logical and easy to use; the collected data were also easy to understand and promoted teacher reflection (e.g. ‘I am now much more aware of my teaching as I have been monitoring my classes for a while’; ‘it helped to see if the method works’) and change in practice (e.g. ‘based on the data I paid more attention to peer communication among students’, ‘I now use more group-work’).

Interestingly, teacher feedback questions concentrated only on students’ classroom experience and progress, and no questions about the teacher activities or impact were actually asked by teachers themselves in our sample. Also, although teachers reported that the tools had helped them to analyse their teaching and expressed their intention to use the tools in their practice, the log data from the tools did not confirm it. The post-intervention interviews (8-10 months later) provide some insight into the reasons, which are mostly linked to time-constraints.

To address the question of discontinued data collection, we wanted to see whether setting an inquiry question by the teacher (in the context of action research within TPD) and using multiple data-sources concurrently (with the hope of getting a broader picture of the classroom reality) enhanced or hindered data collection in the classroom and analysis for classroom practice. Therefore, in our following iteration, we set out to explore the feasibility of using different tools by the same teacher in an action research project (as obviously, in addition to useful information, teachers need some other triggers for data collection to become part of their classroom routine).

3.3 Iteration 3: Effects of regular classroom data collection and analysis on teaching (Study 4)

In this iteration, one teacher used both tools (about twice a month) in her eight-months long action research (Stringer, 2013). We aimed at finding out how the teacher aligns her inquiry questions with

data collection and makes sense of the collected data, and how this might impact her classroom practice.

As video recordings in the classroom are often not allowed, the teacher claimed that her self-tracked logs turned out to be a very good source of information about her different teaching activities used in a lesson (see Table 2). The intervention helped her significantly change the distribution of classroom activities (individual vs group work). For her goal to lead the students towards becoming self-driven learners, the teacher customized Prolearning questions to gather feedback following the SOLO taxonomy (Biggs & Collis, 1982), to make students think about their own learning and development. The teacher considered the tool also good for collecting student anonymous feedback, e.g., to learn about their motivation and engagement in the learning process.

From this small study, we could see that both technological tools proved suitable for the teacher's needs for data collection and helped her in making decisions about her teaching. It also showed that data collection from the physical classroom is feasible if the teacher herself/himself is interested in the data and change in his/her own teaching practice. Despite initial worries about technology use ('took some time to adjust it to the teacher's needs') and strangeness of monitoring one's own teaching ('which eventually became part of the routine'), the tools proved to be helpful for the teacher and could be developed further.

4 Lessons learned and design principles

As in the findings of Dyckhoff et al. (2013), who found that teachers in TEL would use quantitative and qualitative data about student involvement in learning offerings and their rating of these offerings, our study shows that from physical classrooms teachers would also collect data about student motivation, participation and classroom activity patterns. These data, in our case, were collected with the help of technology by the teacher of the class in the form of regular student feedback and classroom activity

logs. This way the teacher was able to determine what data, how and how often to collect, pertaining to their personal needs and interests.

Based on our findings (a list of 14 lessons learned, Table 2), it could be said that technology can support teachers in active data collection about their own classroom teaching if the teacher himself/herself is truly motivated and interested in it (e.g., setting an inquiry question). Otherwise, data-use is often neglected (similarly to automatically-collected data), even when the data have proven to be meaningful for the teacher and help make informed decisions. The main constraints hindering classroom data collection are still shortage of time and intense workload (also indicated by Dillenbourg & Jermann, 2010; Prieto et al., 2020), therefore the tools have to be easy to set up and use, not require much additional effort (to use or analyse the data) and help to collect data that matches the teacher's needs (e.g. classroom activity patterns and student feedback) (similarly voiced by Eradze et al., 2019).

Also, the tools could be semi-automatic (involving the teacher in actively deciding what data to collect and how, but decreasing the workload by automatically analysing and visualizing the collected data) and should trigger teachers' interest to collect data (e.g. possibilities for prediction or comparison seem to motivate teachers). The technology should help teachers be more autonomous in their choices about what data, when and why to collect and/or analyse, therefore the tools should be customizable (Dillenbourg & Jermann, 2010; Authors 2018), yet still easy to use to make the inquiry process simple enough for teachers to implement them (Prieto et al., 2020). It was also interesting to find out about some constraints (teachers' technology preferences, perceptions about the tool use) as well as changes in teacher awareness, reflection and changed practice (see Table 2).

The main changes in classroom practice, which teachers brought out, were linked to switching to more group-work (as compared to individual student tasks), empowering students (deciding on their personal goals and reflecting on their achievement using SOLO taxonomy, and varying classroom

activities.) Student feedback also provided insight into students' group work habits, initiatives ('I asked a question in class', 'I expressed my own idea'), motivation and engagement. Teachers became more reflective and prone to change: 'I am now more aware of my teaching as I have been monitoring my classes for a while', 'the tools made me really think about my teaching and methods that I use', 'my predictions about the lesson did not always match with the students' feedback', or 'based on the responses I rearranged my next class (contents and pace) and paid more attention to peer communication among students'.

Following the lessons learned from our DBR process, we can also propose certain guidelines (Figure 5) for the design of classroom data collection tools:

- 1) The technology should **comply with teachers' data needs and affordances**, but also **trigger teachers' interest** (e.g. through enabling predictions, comparisons and data-download for further analysis (lessons learned 1-4, 10-12, 14)).
- 2) To foster data use (lessons learned 8, 9, 14), **enable teacher-initiated semi-automatic data collection** (as automatic online data is often neglected and paper-based or video-data are time-consuming to analyse).
- 3) **Enable different data types, including teaching data** (our lessons learned 1, 3-6). In our experience, teachers want to collect the length and pattern of classroom activities and (anonymous) student feedback. These, in turn, can be compared with assessment data. .
- 4) The technology should **provide high usability for teachers / be easy to use** despite teacher overload in the classroom (lessons learned 5, 7, 9, 12, 13), and offer **easy to understand visualizations** of the data for analysis (lessons learned 7, 10) .
- 5) **Make the tool customizable** (lessons learned 1-2, 11) - as teachers have different contexts and needs, the technology should allow for some customization (still bearing in mind that the data

should enable comparisons (especially within Multimodal LA) and the tool should be simple to use).

- 6) **Provide some built-in examples** (to imply possible inquiry aspects and trigger interest, lessons learned 7, 10, 14), as a clear inquiry aim is also crucial for meaningful data collection and analysis.

Other findings:

- 7) Also, when possible, **integrate the tool use into the lesson plan** (to comply with the inquiry aim and not to forget the tool use due to classroom constraints).

[Here Figure 5]

5 Conclusions, limitations and further steps

Through a 3-iteration DBR process, this research study attempted to provide an insight into teachers' data needs for informed classroom practice, suggest ways for collecting such data with the help of technology and explore possible effects of the collected data on teachers' practice. Therefore, the paper introduced two teacher-led data collection possibilities for a physical classroom bearing in mind teachers' needs and classroom contextual constraints, and tested the suitability of such data collection options in actual classroom settings. Although the feedback from users was positive, actual adoption into everyday practice after the researchers leave the scene seems insufficient. However, our third iteration shows that long-term usage of the tools is feasible if a teacher is genuinely interested in his/her classroom practice and wants to analyse and keep a record of the processes. To foster usage, the tools have to be easy to use and the data easy to understand; the data collection should be as automatic as possible (not many notes were written down by the teachers) and possibly integrated into the lesson and with other classroom technologies already in use. Most importantly, the data collection technology

should cater for teachers' specific needs for classroom data, e.g., include varied data and be customizable.

The main limitation of our research is the small number of teachers who have used such data collection means so far. Also, the reliability of the scales was not tested as the Likert scale questions in the first iteration were used to probe teachers' preferences for data collection technology and their current data use habits, with no intention for generalizations. For the second iteration, the questions were based on the Technology Acceptance Model (Davis, 1989; Venkatesh & Davis, 2000), but due to such a small sample, no generalizations were intended and only descriptive analysis was used. However, to strengthen the research design, the questionnaire and interview data about the use of the tools were triangulated with log data from the tools used in the classrooms.

The next step in our research would be the implementation of an in-action technology-enhanced teacher-led inquiry with multiple tools (e.g., to support different phases of the inquiry process, not only the data gathering) for a longer period of time, to track their actual adoption and find out about the impact of such data collection on teachers' classroom practice and student success. We will also continue with further development of the tools themselves, to provide a richer picture of the classroom (e.g., its activities and atmosphere) in order to detect the possible changes in teachers' practice due to their data use.

To further triangulate the data, it would be useful to add some easy-to-use tools which would provide data about student motivation and involvement (e.g. sensor data), teacher talk (clarity of explanations, tone) and would help collate different data into a meaningful overview of a class taught, connecting it to student success (progress and satisfaction).

References

Ali, L., Hatala, M., Gašević, D., & Jovanović, J. (2012). A qualitative evaluation of evolution of a learning analytics tool. *Computers & Education*, 58(1), 470–489.

- Berliner, D. C. (2001). Learning about and learning from expert teachers. *International journal of educational research*, 35(5), 463-482.
- Biggs, J. B., & Collis, K. F. (1982). *Evaluating the quality of learning: The SOLO taxonomy (Structure of the Observed Learning Outcome)*. New York: Academic Press.
- Datnow, A., & Hubbard, L. (2016). Teacher capacity for and beliefs about data-driven decision making: A literature review of international research. *Journal of Educational Change*, 17(1), 7–28.
- Dillenbourg, P., & Jermann, P. (2010). Technology for classroom orchestration. In *New science of learning* (pp. 525-552). Springer, New York, NY.
- Dyckhoff, A. L., Lukarov, V., Muslim, A., Chatti, M. A., & Schroeder, U. (2013, April). Supporting action research with learning analytics. In *Proceedings of the Third International Conference on Learning Analytics and Knowledge* (pp. 220-229). ACM.
- Eradze, M., Rodríguez-Triana, M. J., & Laanpere, M. (2019). A Conversation between Learning Design and Classroom Observations: A Systematic Literature Review. *Education Sciences*, 9(2), 91.
- Estapa, A. & Amador, J. (2016). Wearable Cameras As A Tool To Capture Preservice Teachers' Marked And Recorded Noticing. *Journal of Technology and Teacher Education*, 24(3), 281-307.
- Estonian Lifelong Learning Strategy 2020. <https://www.hm.ee/en/estonian-lifelong-learning-strategy-2020>
- Feng, M., Krumm, A. E., Bowers, A. J., & Podkul, T. (2016, April). Elaborating data intensive research methods through researcher-practitioner partnerships. In *Proceedings of the Sixth International Conference on Learning Analytics & Knowledge* (pp. 540–541).
- Goertz, M. E., Olah, L. N., & Riggan, M. (2009). *From Testing to Teaching: The Use of Interim Assessments in Classroom Instruction*. CPRE Research Reports, 253.
- Gummer, E., & Mandinach, E. (2015). Building a Conceptual Framework for Data Literacy. *Teachers College Record*, 117(4).
- Hernández-Leo, D., Martínez-Maldonado, R., Pardo, A., Muñoz-Cristóbal, J. A., & Rodríguez-Triana, M. J. (2019). Analytics for learning design: A layered framework and tools. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 50(1), 139-152.

- Holstein, K., McLaren, B. M., & Alevan, V. (2017, March). Intelligent tutors as teachers' aides: exploring teacher needs for real-time analytics in blended classrooms. In *Proceedings of the Seventh International Learning Analytics & Knowledge Conference* (pp. 257-266).
- Hubers, M. D., Poortman, C. L., Schildkamp, K., Pieters, J. M., & Handelzalts, A. (2016). Opening the black box: knowledge creation in data teams. *Journal of Professional Capital and Community*, 1(1), 41–68.
- Ingram, D., Louis, K. S., & Schroeder, R. G. (2004). Accountability Policies and Teacher Decision Making: Barriers to the Use of Data to Improve Practice. *Teachers College Record*, 106(6), 1258–1287.
- Jimerson, J. B., & Wayman, J. C. (2015). Professional learning for using data: Examining teacher needs and supports. *Teachers College Record*, 117(4), n4.
- Kaufman, T., Graham, C. R., Picciano, A. G., Wiley, D., & Popham, J. A. (2014). Data-driven decision making in the k12 classroom. In J. M. Spector, M. D. Merrill, J. Elen, & M. J. Bishop (Eds.), *Handbook of research on educational communications and technology* (4th ed, pp. 337–346). New York, NY: Springer.
- Lai, M. K., & Schildkamp, K. (2013). Data-based Decision Making: An Overview. In Kim Schildkamp, M. K. Lai, & L. Earl (Eds.), *Data-based Decision Making in Education* (pp. 9–21). Dordrecht: Springer Netherlands.
- Mangaroska, K., & Giannakos, M. N. (2018). Learning analytics for learning design: A systematic literature review of analytics-driven design to enhance learning. *IEEE Transactions on Learning Technologies*, 1–1.
- Mandinach, E. B., Honey, M., & Light, D. (2006, April). A theoretical framework for data-driven decision making. In: *Annual meeting of the American Educational Research Association*, San Francisco, CA.
- Mandinach, E. B. (2012). A perfect time for data use: Using data-driven decision making to inform practice. *Educational Psychologist*, 47(2), 71-85.
- Martinez-Maldonado, R., Elliott, D., Axisa, C., Power, T., Echeverria, V., & Buckingham Shum, S. (2020). Designing translucent learning analytics with teachers: an elicitation process. *Interactive Learning Environments*, 1-15.
- Pierce, R., Chick, H., & Gordon, I. (2013). Teachers' perceptions of the factors influencing their engagement with statistical reports on student achievement data. *Australian Journal of Education*, 57(3), 237–255.

- Prieto, L. P., Magnuson, P., Dillenbourg, P., & Saar, M. (2020). Reflection for action: Designing tools to support teacher reflection on everyday evidence. *Technology, Pedagogy and Education*, 1-17. Prieto, L. P., Sharma, K., Wen, Y., & Dillenbourg, P. (2015). The burden of facilitating collaboration: towards estimation of teacher orchestration load using eye-tracking measures. International Society of the Learning Sciences, Inc. [ISLS].
- Prieto, L. P., Wen, Y., Caballero, D., & Dillenbourg, P. (2014). Review of augmented paper systems in education: An orchestration perspective. *Journal of Educational Technology & Society*, 17(4), 169-185.
- Reeves, T. D., & Honig, S. L. (2015). A classroom data literacy intervention for pre-service teachers. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 50, 90–101.
- Rienties, B., & Toetenel, L. (2016). The impact of learning design on student behaviour, satisfaction and performance: A cross-institutional comparison across 151 modules. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 60, 333-341.
- Authors (2018). Reference anonymized for peer review.
- Authors (2019). Reference anonymized for peer review.
- Schildkamp, K. & Kuiper, W. (2010). Data-informed curriculum reform: Which data, what purposes, and promoting and hindering factors. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 26(3), 482–496.
- Schildkamp, K., Poortman, C. L., & Handelzalts, A. (2016). Data teams for school improvement. *School Effectiveness and School Improvement*, 27(2), 228–254.
- Sergis, S., & Sampson, D. G. (2017). Teaching and learning analytics to support teacher inquiry: A systematic literature review. In: *Learning analytics: Fundamentals, applications, and trends* (pp. 25-63). Springer, Cham.
- Sergis, S., Sampson, D. G., Rodríguez-Triana, M. J., Gillet, D., Pelliccione, L., & de Jong, T. (2019). Using educational data from teaching and learning to inform teachers' reflective educational design in inquiry-based STEM education. *Computers in human behavior*, 92, 724-738.
- Stringer, E. T. (2013). *Action research*. Sage publications.
- Supovitz, J.A. (2013). *The linking study: An experiment to strengthen teachers' engagement with data on teaching and learning*.
- Venkatesh, V., & Davis, F. D. (2000). A theoretical extension of the technology acceptance model: Four longitudinal field studies. *Management science*, 46(2), 186-204.
- Wang, F., & Hannafin, M. J. (2005). Design-based research and technology-enhanced learning environments. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 53(4), 5–23.

